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Conflicting Conceptualisation of Europeanisation

Poland Country Report

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List of Abbreviations

AMIF – Asylum Migration and Integration Fund

KORWIN – Koalicja Odnowy Rzeczypospolitej Wolność i Nadzieja (KORWIN - Coalition for the Renewal of the Republic – Liberty and Hope)

PiS – Prawo i Sprawiedliwość (Law and Justice)

PO – Platforma Obywatelska (Civic Platform)

PSL – Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe (Polish People's Party)

SLD – Democratic Left Alliance (Sojusz Lewicy Demokratycznej)

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About the project

RESPOND is a Horizon 2020 project which aims at studying the multilevel governance of migration in Europe and beyond. The consortium is formed of **14 partners from 11 source, transit and destination countries and is coordinated by Uppsala University in Sweden.** The main aim of this Europe-wide project is to provide an **in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration** on macro-, meso- and micro-levels through cross-country comparative research, and to critically analyse governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its member states and third countries.

RESPOND will study migration governance through a narrative which is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanisation. Each thematic field reflects a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and has been designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impacts, and responses given by affected actors within.

In order to better focus on these themes, we divided our research question into work packages (WPs). The present report is concerned with the findings related to WP5, which focuses specifically on integration policies and practices.

Executive summary/Abstract

This report aims to present the results of research on migration discourse and its effect on Europeanisation in Poland. The main objective of the research was to examine how political elite discourse on increasing external migration to the EU is framed in media and deliberated among stakeholders with regard to the course of Europeanisation. The research was based on a three-step analytical process: analysis of political speeches, analysis of the media, and analysis of stakeholder's opinions. Furthermore, the research was a part of one of the work packages of the Horizon 2020 project RESPOND: Multi-level migration governance in Europe and beyond.

The crucial themes of this report are migration discourses and the narratives of Europeanisation. The discourse of migration in Poland began in 2015 and it was an effect of the so-called 'refugee crisis' (or 'migration crisis') in Europe coinciding with the electoral campaign before the parliamentary elections held on 25 October that year. The discourse was triggered not so much by the arrival of asylum seekers in Poland, which was minimal in numbers, but by the European debate on relocation quotas of refugees among the EU Member States. Although there had been political debates on migration, refugee admission and the principle of solidarity prior to 2015, their publicity was of minor significance. Since 2015, rival political parties in Poland have been shaping their own approaches towards migration, especially forced migration, although not all of them distinguish asylum seekers as a different category of immigrants. Significantly, the crystallization of the political actors' approaches towards migration coincided with increasing opposition against Europeanisation as a whole or against chosen aspects of it such as burden sharing in the face of the crisis. The main research question therefore is as follows: Did the migration discourse trigger the increasing opposition of political parties against the European Union in Poland?

The three-step analysis proved that the political and media debate about the two issues – forced migration and Poland's integration with the EU – are closely related to each other and often form part of the same discourse. It appeared that the political party system in Poland and lack of an influential left or social democratic party strong enough to be a dominant force in the parliament impacted the traditional division of Liberal and Conservative parties and led to conservative dominance of political discourse. Contrary to the political parties, the analysed newspapers – the liberal *Gazeta Wyborcza*, the centrist *Rzeczpospolita*, and the conservative (arguably far-right) *Gazeta Polska Codziennie* – presented a much broader spectrum of opinions on migration and Europeanisation. While two of the selected newspapers fit in well in the ideological division between Liberal Europeanisers (*Gazeta Wyborcza*) and Conservative Europeaniser (*Rzeczpospolita*), the third – *Gazeta Polska Codziennie* – could be deemed anti-EU in its stance.

Introduction

The report presents findings of the research on Conflicting Europeanisation conducted within Work Package 6 (WP6) of the RESPOND project. It examines how conflicting political elite discourses of Europeanisation in Poland have emerged in the context of increasing migration to the European Union. The report has the following objectives:

- to look at the construction of political claims in Poland about forced migration to the European Union,
- to capture the recent evolution of Polish discourses on Europeanisation,
- to frame Polish Europeanisation discourses in the context of migration.

Furthermore, this report assesses how these ideas and claims are constructed by political actors, interpreted in the mass media, and deliberated by the project stakeholders. Rather than concentrating on policy developments, WP6 addresses how increases in external migration have created both anti-migration and anti-European discourses.

The background of this report is the refugee crisis of 2015, caused by increased forced migration to Europe and a lack of efficient coordination among the EU member states toward this issue. In Poland this precipitated a public debate on refugee admission. However, the fierce political and public contestation on refugees in Poland was actually triggered by two mutually interlinked developments: the refugee relocation scheme discussed from April 2015 and approved in September 2015 and the welcoming policy of German Chancellor Angela Merkel, who in early 2015 started advocating for EU countries to support asylum seekers and later in August 2015 declared that Germany would admit all Syrian asylum seekers coming to Europe (Łotocki 2019, pp. 143-151).

In September 2015, based on the proposal of the European Commission, the Justice and Home Affairs Council (comprised of interior ministers of the European Union Member States) decided to introduce an Emergency Relocation System (quota system for refugee relocations). It aimed at supporting the frontline states of Italy and Greece in admission of asylum seekers by relocating 160,000 refugees to other EU countries. Not without significance in the Polish context was the fact that the new system of refugee relocation was proposed by Angela Merkel. The Czech Republic, Hungary, Romania, and Slovakia voted against the relocation system, whereas Poland, then ruled by PM Ewa Kopacz (Civic Platform) accepted it, issuing a promise to accommodate 7,200 refugees in the forthcoming years (Pędzwiatr and Legut 2018). However, the Law and Justice party, which came to power after the October 2015 elections, disregarded Poland's commitments on this matter by first lowering the number of anticipated admission of refugees to 400 in January 2016, and then rescinding the plans of relocation to Poland of the first 100 refugees (65 from Greece and 35 from Italy) in May 2016 (Łotocki 2019, pp. 176-177).

A consequence of the fierce political debate was a protracted public debate which impacted the Polish society's attitudes towards foreigners, especially refugees. Between 2015 and 2017, Poles changed from being cautious supporters to decisive opponents of admitting refugees into the country. According to an IOM/Ipsos opinion poll (2016), nearly two-thirds of Poles had some concerns about the inflow of foreigners to Poland, regardless of whether they had had any contact with foreigners in the last year. Surprisingly, far more respondents consider the impact of migrants on the economy and labour market as negative (45%) than

positive (25%). The prevailing negative attitudes towards foreigners or towards admitting refugees were reflected in surveys by CBOS (2018, 2017, 2016) and IPSOS (2016, 2015).

The newly emerged migration discourses have from the very beginning been closely related to Europeanisation. Europeanisation in Poland started as early as the early 1990s as a consequence of interactions between Polish and European policy-makers and Polish and international institutions. The main channel of Europeanisation facilitating the policy learning and policy transfer, however, was the accession negotiation process, with the leading role of the European Commission and EU conditionality mechanisms (Weinar 2007, p. 5).

The migration discourses mostly impacted the political dimension of Europeanisation in Poland with reference to the conservative narrative of safeguarding the nation state against the dictates of the EU. Since coming to power in 2015, the Law and Justice party (*Prawo i Sprawiedliwość*, PiS) has been expressing its discontent with the EU and the European model of society. The ideological roots of this discontent, also called de-Europeanisation, resting primarily in deeply ingrained convictions about nation, culture, and Europe within the ruling PiS party and among its zealots. In this sense, PiS has intentionally moved away from the path adopted by the Polish governments in the 1990s and early 2000s in their quest for modernisation and Europeanisation. Significantly, the PiS government diverted from framing the EU as an opportunity for Poland and started to portray it as a risk instead (Buras 2017).

Methodology

The main objective of this Work Package of the RESPOND project was to examine how elite discourse on increasing external migration to the EU is framed in media and deliberated among stakeholders with regard to the course of Europeanisation. The research was based on a three-step analysis, where each step contained different research material:

Step 1: Analysis of political speeches: Direct speeches (non-mediatised material) of major political party actors containing explicit references to the future of the EU and developments in the policy field of migration – 22 speeches

Step 2: Media analysis: 51 selected newspaper columns/editorials from three Polish newspapers: *Rzeczpospolita*, *Gazeta Wyborcza* and *Gazeta Polska Codziennie* (17 articles from each newspaper).

Step 3: Stakeholders' opinions analysis: Q&A session with stakeholders involved in multi-level governance of migration in Poland conducted as a part of a Migration Governance Network meeting held in the Centre of Migration Research (University of Warsaw) on 16 January 2020.

In order to conduct the political speeches analysis, 22 speeches of leaders of the main political parties in Poland were selected (Appendix A). The main parties were chosen according to their performance in the parliamentary elections held in October 2015. Only those which registered lists of candidates to the Sejm (Lower Chamber of the Polish Parliament) in at least half of the constituencies and gained more than 3 percent¹ of the votes in the elections were included. According to the outcomes of parliamentary elections in Poland in 2015, there were eight such parties (including one electoral alliance): Law and Justice (*Prawo i Sprawiedliwość*, PiS), Civic Platform (*Platforma Obywatelska*, PO), Kukiz'15, Modern (*Nowoczesna*), United Left (*Zjednoczona Lewica*) (electoral alliance), Polish People's Party (*Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe*, PSL), KORWiN (Coalition for the Renewal of the Republic – Liberty and Hope), and Together (*Razem*).

The selection of the speeches was based on the RESPOND project criteria:

- Direct speeches (non-mediatised material) of major political party actors containing explicit references to the future of the EU and developments in the policy field of migration – 15-20 speeches. The political actors exclusively encompass politicians leading or serving in the central government, and leaders of opposition parties.
- Time frame: April 2011 - July 2018.
- Related to increased migration to the European Union.

Being aware of national specificities in each country of the RESPOND project, it was decided to apply a simplified division of ideologies, mirroring the politicians' stances towards forced migration. On that account the identified themes were assigned as belonging to one of two groups: Liberal Europeaniser or Conservative Europeaniser. Within the RESPOND project we defined 'Liberal Europeaniser' as pro-diversity and pro-equality for all, including third-country nationals, and seeking to entrench openness as a fundamental element for the future course of Europeanisation. This role-bearer believes in an internationalist EU that is ready for

¹ Although the threshold to gain seats in parliament in Poland is 5% for a political party and 8% for an electoral alliance, the result of a minimum 3% of votes entitles a party to receive a subsidy from the state budget.

involvement in external assistance and humanitarian aid. This role accepts respect for universal human dignity as a pillar European identity. It is pro-solidarity regarding burden-sharing and refugee quotas and relocation within the EU (Korkut 2017). Respectively, 'Conservative Europeaniser' has been defined as defensive of the West, rationalising this defence with the need to protect Judeo-Christian civilisation by rejecting non-Westerners. 'Non-Western' is a highly contextual term in its reference to religion, ethnicity and race. Furthermore, this defence implies a non-interference role for Europe in external development aid and humanitarian aid. This role is highly security-focused both internally and externally. It is also heteronormative on diversity issues (Korkut 2017).

Matching the themes as representing the views of either Liberal Europeanisers or Conservative Europeanisers has been done inductively, meaning that self-identification of political parties with any ideology was not considered.

With regard to media articles, we exclusively focused on opinion pieces/editorials, based on the assumption that this is a debate-focused genre encompassing longer discussions of an issue and revealing more of the ideational twist that a newspaper brings to social and political debate. We focused on articles that thematically elaborate on the types of narratives identified in step 1. The articles were selected from three Polish national newspapers: liberal *Gazeta Wyborcza*; centrist, with a bias towards conservatism, *Rzeczpospolita*; and conservative, far-right *Gazeta Polska Codziennie*. The selected articles either directly or indirectly discuss the respective narrative identified in the first step of the research (political claims analysis). Then we analysed how narratives are debated within newspapers across the political spectrum. Building on Scholten and Dekker's (2017, p. 208) approach within their analysis of media effects on Dutch immigration policies, we used the following analytical grid for coding:

- How does the editor of the article interpret a claim presented by a politician?
- How does he/she interpret the situation as it already exists?
- What is the causal narrative explaining why a particular issue arose?
- How is the politician/party raising the claims portrayed?
- How is the target group portrayed?
- What is the strategy for solving the issue and how is it seen by the newspaper?

In order to answer the above questions, I used a discursive frame (Foucault 1969, Entman 1993, Ensink and Sauer 2003, Korkut and Eslen-Ziya 2018). Discourse as defined by Foucault is "*an entity of sequences, of signs, in that they are statements (énoncés)*" (Foucault 1969). 'Frame' refers to the fact that discourse participants share the overall sense of the function of the discourse in the social situation (Ensink and Sauer 2003). Frames also provide some structure for the discourse: in a way they "*define problems – determine what a causal agent is doing with what costs and benefits, usually measured in terms of common cultural values; diagnose causes – identify the forces creating the problem; make moral judgments – evaluate causal agents and their effects; and suggest remedies – offer and justify treatments for the problems and predict their likely effects*" (Entman 1993, p. 52).

Third, we conducted a Questions & Answers session with 17 stakeholders during the Migration Governance Network Roundtable meeting held on 16 January 2020 in the Centre of Migration Research at the University of Warsaw. The stakeholders comprised representatives of social organisations (6 persons), public institutions (4), international organisations (1), the

Catholic Church (2) and academia (4). The topics of the discussion were related to migration discourses in Poland, the role of the EU in the migration crisis, and the future of Europeanisation.

As regards the term 'Europeanisation', in this report it is understood according to the most frequently cited definition of Radaelli, who defined it as a set of processes of (a) construction (b) diffusion and (c) institutionalization of formal and informal rules, procedures, policy paradigms, styles, "ways of doing things" and shared beliefs and norms which are first defined and consolidated in the making of EU decisions and then incorporated into the logic of domestic discourse, identities, political structures, and public policies (Radaelli, 2004: 30).

Referring to the above definition, Europeanisation happens in many different dimensions: from geographical, sociological, and educational to economic, legal, institutional, political, and geopolitical. In this report the main focus is on the political dimension, in the spirit of which Europeanisation leads to delegation of competencies of the national governments to the EU-level (be it the European Council, the Council of the European Union, or the European Commission). In this sense, Europeanisation impacts the national states, in particular their political structures, decision-making processes, and functions. It is especially visible in the balancing of political powers (Europeanisation of political systems) and the emerging of the EU political system (Wach 2013, pp. 40-41).

The discourses on migration and Europeanisation have been related to each other because they both refer to identity and to categories of home, belonging, and otherness. Due to exclusion of immigration from the scope of policies of the European Union, immigration policy has become a particularly interesting field from the perspective of Europeanisation, because it deals with a Member State's sovereignty over the entry and residence of non-citizens in its territory (Ette and Faist, 2007).

Party-Political Structure: Developments since 2011

Following the fall of communism in 1989, a new system of government was introduced in Poland based on the division of power, political pluralism, and a parliamentary-cabinet form of government with a relatively strong position of the President (Jaskiernia, 2015, p. 79).²

Since 1989, the political party system in Poland has undergone democratic transformation from a hegemonic party (Sartori, 1976) to a multi-party system. The development of the multi-party system aimed at (re)creation of a western pattern of political competition was achieved through adopting a new Electoral Law that included democratic regulations of establishing and financing political parties (Antoszewski 1995, p. 15). In effect it was also a part of the Europeanisation process of Poland. In addition to the system transformation, which has obviously had a significant influence on the Polish political scene, the Polish party system has been also shaped by the legacy of the Solidarity movement of the 1980s. The issues of being or not being a member of the Solidarity trade union and the significance of particular politicians in the movement have frequently been brought to light and have become the cause of political controversies. In addition, “the religious and national values, as well as the historical and cultural issues, which emerged into the daylight, may be treated as the embryo of certain ideas, which in time, as a result of public debates, have become fundamental determinants of many political parties” (Górka, 2010, p. 77).

In 2011, which is a starting point of the analysis determined by the RESPOND project criteria (breakout of the Syrian Civil War), the Polish political party system was dominated by a rivalry between Law and Justice and Civic Platform which dates back to the early 2000s, and the waning role of the biggest Polish left-wing party Democratic Left Alliance (*Sojusz Lewicy Demokratycznej*, SLD) which was until 2005 either the ruling party (between 1993-1997 and 2001-2005) or the main opposition party (between 1997-2001) in Poland. That year saw the first Law and Justice government, followed in 2007 by the first Civic Platform government. In 2011 Civic Platform won the parliamentary elections, receiving 39% of votes and 45% of seats in the Sejm (the lower chamber of the Polish parliament), and thereupon formed a coalition government with the Polish People's Party (*Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe*, PSL). Law and Justice, with nearly 30% of votes, retained its position as the main opposition party. In 2015, Law and Justice gained 37% percent of votes and 51% of seats, which enabled the party to form the first majority one-party government in Poland since 1991. Civic Platform gained 24% of votes and 30% of the seats in the Sejm. This was also the first year in the post-communist history of Poland when the Democratic Left Alliance or any other left-wing party did not win seats in the parliament³. The other three parties which entered the Sejm were anti-establishment centre-right KWW Kukiz'15, centre-right and liberal Modern, and the mentioned PSL. It is worth adding here that in 2015 a PiS-supported candidate (Andrzej Duda) won the presidential elections. Thus, for the first time after 1989 a single political party had full control over executive and legislative powers.

The parliamentary elections in 2019 brought further strengthening of the support for PiS (43.5% of votes, 51% of seats in the Sejm). Civic Platform, as a part of Civic Coalition (*Koalicja*

² Stronger than in model parliamentary-cabinet governments, but not as strong as in presidential or semi-presidential systems.

³ In 2015 PiS was able to secure a majority of seats in the Sejm with lower electoral support than PO had in 2011 due to the fact that SLD support placed it just below the electoral threshold for alliance of political parties.

Obywatelska, KO) together with the Modern, the Green, and the Silesian Autonomy Movement, gained 27% of votes and 29% of seats. However, considering the fact that the two biggest parties in the KO, that is Civic Platform and the Modern, gained in the previous elections 31% of votes in total, the 2019 elections results were slightly worse. The other three political groups to succeed in entering parliament were: SLD (12.5% of votes, 10.5% of seats), PSL (8.5% of votes, 6.5% of seats) and far-right Confederation Liberty and Independence (*Konfederacja Wolność i Niepodległość*, *Konfederacja*) (nearly 7% of votes, 2.4% of seats). Democratic Left Alliance (SLD) managed to return to parliament owing to joining its forces with two other left-wing parties, Spring (*Wiosna*) and Together (*Razem*). Another change was entering the parliament by the hard-line Eurosceptic *Konfederacja*, which brought together libertarian conservatives (Coalition for the Renewal of the Republic – Liberty and Hope, KORWiN) and the nationalist ultra-right National Movement party. Hard Euroscepticism (also called anti-EU-ism) is "a principled opposition to the EU and European integration and therefore can be seen in parties who think that their countries should withdraw from membership, or whose policies towards the EU are tantamount to being opposed to the whole project of European integration as it is currently conceived." (Szczerbiak and Bill 2008, p. 7).

Since Poland's accession to the EU in 2004, the Polish political parties' interest in European issues has been deepening, especially during the EU crises. However, joining the EU coincided with shifting the main axis of political division in Poland from left-right into liberalism-social conservatism,⁴ thereupon European values and stances towards them have become one of the main themes of political debate. All Polish governments after 2004 emphasized the slogan of "strong Poland in a strong Europe", which means they were oriented towards the implementation of national interests and at the same time supported the development of European integration. All of them refrained from the idea of building a federation in the EU, and criticized the idea of a "two-speed Europe" (Grosse 2018). During the 'refugee crisis' of 2015, politicians from the largest parties (Law and Justice, Civic Platform, Modern) emphasized the protection of the EU's external borders. As a rule, they expressed distance from or even opposition to permanent mechanisms for the relocation of refugees.

The Law and Justice party, in line with the Polish doctrine of European policy, rejected the federal development of integration. The party program stressed that the EU should remain a community of sovereign and equal nations. Another key element of the program has been opposition to the growing power of the largest member states in the integration processes. PiS emphasized that democracy in Europe occurs primarily in national states, which is why it is so important to respect both the subjectivity of all governments and the voices of national parliaments in politics and decisions taken at the EU level. Despite being opposed to the division into a "two-speed Europe", the party is in favour of strengthening cooperation in Central Europe, including deepening cooperation within the Visegrad Group and the Three Seas Initiative. This is to balance the domination of the Franco-German tandem in the EU and the predominance of Western European interests over the Central European perspective. PiS politicians are against further centralization of powers in the EU, and thus would like to slow down the progress of integration (Grosse 2018). With respect to the 'migration crisis', the PiS government disagreed with the compulsory quotas for the relocation of refugees, and

⁴ Since the parliamentary elections in 2005 when the main political struggle took place between two parties with a post-Solidarity lineage, Civic Platform (*Platforma Obywatelska*, PO) and Law and Justice (PiS), the new ideological division has been shaped on the axis of social conservatism (called also social solidarity) versus liberalism. See more at: Jasiewicz, 2008; Markowski, Czeńnik and Kotnarowski, 2011; Flis and Kwiatkowska, 2018.

proposed to strengthen the EU's external borders and to intensify humanitarian and development policy activities outside the EU (Grosse 2018).

Civic Platform, the largest opposition party, has been supporting the further development of European integration for years. For example, it supported the strengthening of the European Commission as an institution intended to contribute to the protection of the interests of smaller Member States. Some statements of PO politicians were supportive towards federalization of the EU, for example expressing support for the idea of a pan-European list of candidates for the EP elections. At the same time, these politicians called for keeping a number of competences in the domain of the member states, especially with regard to "national identity, religion, lifestyle, public morality and tax rates". (Grosse 2018). In 2015, the PO government supported the EU regulation on compulsory quotas for the relocation of refugees in the EU. Influenced by public opinion and as a result of lost elections, PO tightened the party position on this matter, recognizing that the division of refugees must be voluntary and the emphasis in EU policy should be on the control of the EU's external borders. At the same time, the head of the Civic Platform promised not to accept illegal migrants should he take power. In this way, the position of this party towards migration has clearly come close to the policy of the ruling PiS (Grosse 2018).

Media Structure and the Question of Europeanisation

The Polish media landscape has been shaped by the country's socio-political and economic transition after the fall of communism in 1989. Since then the most important features of the media system in Poland have been the following: privatisation of the press sector; the transformation of state radio and television into public broadcasting organisations; licensing of private broadcasters; an influx of foreign capital into the Polish media market; and Europeanisation of audio-visual media policies. In the first decade after 1989, the Polish audio-visual media sector grew rapidly. These developments led to the establishment of a public and private duopoly of television and radio (Lara 2013), whereas print media are private, with a significant presence of foreign investors (Dobek-Ostrowska 2012: 31-32). The latter is an effect of penetration of Poland's newly opened media market by foreign publishers during the economic transformation. This resulted in a high degree of market concentration in the hands of big publishers (Agora, Bauer, Ringier Axel Springer) controlling "more newspapers, more magazines, more television channels, and more radio stations and, as McQuail (2005) claims, with increased power" (Dobek-Ostrowska 2012: 31-32). Another consequence of foreign ownership of media outlets is strong commercialization and tabloidization of the media system (Dobek-Ostrowska, 2012: 31-32).

Currently, Poland has more than 6,000 press titles, including national and regional dailies, weeklies, monthly magazines, and the specialised press. None of the Polish dailies publish on Sunday or in the afternoon. Instead, Polish dailies offer weekend editions, which tend to have significantly higher circulation than weekday editions (Dzierżyńska-Mielczarek 2017, p. 8).

In 2018, the circulation of the two largest national dailies (both tabloids) reached over 360,000 copies for Fakt, and 200,000 for Super Express. The next places were taken by three high-quality newspapers: Gazeta Wyborcza (150,589 copies), Rzeczpospolita (57,238) and Dziennik Gazeta Prawna (45,281). Gazeta Polska Codziennie, with a quite large circulation (61,239 copies) had relatively small sales (15,388 copies). However, it was the only far-right daily present among the nine national newspapers with the biggest circulation. Other national dailies included in the list were more specialised outlets: Przegląd Sportowy (53,687 copies), which focuses on sport, and two business newspapers, Puls Biznesu (11,749 copies) and Parkiet Gazeta Giełdy (6,646 copies) (see Table 1).

Table 1 – Newspapers circulation in Poland in 2017-2018

Newspaper	Year			
	2017		2018	
	Circulation (average per day)	Sales (average per day)	Circulation (average per day)	Sales (average per day)
Fakt Gazeta Codziennie	387,276	261,395	363,152	237,700
Super Express	224,329	129,322	204,192	118,370
Gazeta Wyborcza	190,867	124,173	160,589	106,227
Rzeczpospolita	70,612	48,949	57,238	45,108
Dziennik Gazeta Prawna	49,168	45,502	45,281	41,366

Przegląd Sportowy	54,547	25,843	53,687	23,832
Gazeta Polska Codziennie	67,844	18,214	61,239	15,388
Puls Biznesu	12,002	11,780	11,749	11,473
Parkiet Gazeta Gieldy	10,533	4,421	6,646	4,150

Source: Związek Kontroli Dystrybucji Prasy (ZKDP) (2019, 2018).

In total, in Poland there are more than ten newspapers representing different political orientations and ideologies. Quality newspapers (Gazeta Wyborcza, Rzeczpospolita and Dziennik Gazeta Prawna) are addressed to a small elite – mainly urban, well educated, and politically active readers. A strong segment of tabloids and free newspapers is present in Poland, with blue-collar workers and smaller-town and rural residents being the main target (Dobek-Ostrowska, 2012: 32). In addition, there are also far-right newspapers and periodicals (Nasz Dziennik, Gazeta Polska, Gazeta Polska Codziennie, wSieci, Do Rzeczy) addressed to conservative or ultra-Catholic and nationalist readers, which has its reflection in, or a correlation with, the increasing electoral support for far-right political parties.

With respect to the three newspapers selected to the research, Rzeczpospolita, Gazeta Wyborcza and Gazeta Polska Codziennie, they can be described as liberal (Gazeta Wyborcza), neutral with a conservative inclination (Rzeczpospolita), and conservative far-right (Gazeta Polska Codziennie).

Rzeczpospolita is a conservative daily newspaper, but it has clearly distanced itself from the national-conservative governing party PiS since the latter took office at the end of 2015. The paper is primarily critical of the government's foreign policy and the party's increasing control over democratic institutions. The pro-European Rzeczpospolita is the only conservative media outlet in Poland to advocate the country's accession to Eurozone.⁵ Gazeta Wyborcza, identified as a liberal, centre-left and pro-European newspaper, is highly critical of the PiS government, and frequently calls for protests against the government⁶. Gazeta Polska Codziennie with its far-right political orientation represents a conservative to nationalist standpoint and has close ties to the ruling PiS party.⁷

Resulting from both political culture and tradition, the media in Poland have been politicized. Publicly owned media (television TVP S.A. and Polskie Radio) have been dominated directly by political actors since the beginning of the post-communist transformation, being controlled by the political group in power at any time. Private opinion media owned by Polish capital do not have any formal connection with political parties, although they have their own political sympathies and antipathies expressed in more or less obvious ways. The third group, the media belonging to foreign companies, above all the tabloids, tries to be neutral because they are concerned with their business (Dobek-Ostrowska, 2012: 37-38).

After the coming to power of Law and Justice in 2015, media in Poland have become polarised due to direct or indirect support offered by the party to pro-government media while targeting critical journalists, sometimes with the assistance of law enforcement agencies

⁵ <https://www.eurotopics.net/en/148775/rzeczpospolita#> [Accessed 1 August 2020]

⁶ <https://www.eurotopics.net/en/148554/gazeta-wyborcza> [Accessed 1 August 2020]

⁷ <https://www.eurotopics.net/en/148553/gazeta-polska-codziennie> [Accessed 1 August 2020]

(Makarenko 2019). The public television TVP, dependent on financial support from the government, has become an instrument of propaganda for PiS. Apart from controlling the public TV and radio stations (Polskie Radio) the government continues to support a number of other media companies through the substantial advertising spending of state enterprises and agencies. The main beneficiaries are the pro-government newspaper titles such as *Gazeta Polska*, *w Sieci*, and *Do Rzeczy*. For them, state-related revenues accounted for 45%, 40%, and 23% of total advertising revenues respectively (Makarenko 2019).

With reference to the media in general and newspapers in particular, stances on the European Union, politicians and journalists in Poland tend to be much more Eurosceptic than the public, according to research (Jakubowski 2019, Łotocki 2019). Regular studies commissioned by the European Commission clearly indicate that Poles are among the least Eurosceptic nations in the EU. In 2019, 68% of Poles believed that EU membership was generally beneficial (7% more than the EU average). Moreover, there is a greater diversity of press titles containing Eurosceptic content, including both conservative and left-liberal press in the top three. There is also a tendency of the pro-European press to discuss topics and cite statements resulting from anti-European attitudes, which may mean that they were attractive and thus eagerly tackled, regardless of the ideological position of a given press title on the axes of socio-political divisions (Jakubowski 2019, p. 226).

Headlines and Events Impacting Asylum/Migration Discourse since 2011

In Poland, the forced migration discourse started in 2015 as a direct result of an increased inflow of forced migrants to Europe (but not to Poland) and negotiations within the EU on a refugee relocation scheme in the same year. The discourse was somewhat heralded by the outbreak of the military conflict between Russia and Ukraine in the east of Ukraine in early 2014, in the aftermath of which the Polish government expected numbers of Ukrainians would be seeking asylum in Poland. Before 2014 there were hardly any mentions to be found in any political or public debate about forced migrants coming to Europe.

Surprisingly, unlike in many other European countries, the migration discourse in Poland was not triggered by increasing numbers of asylum seekers in the country. The net migration substantially increased to 1.8 million (the number of all visas, both Schengen and national, issued by Polish consulates) in 2016 (Szulecka, Pachocka, Sobczak-Szelc 2018, p. 13), but this was caused by labour migrants, whose presence did not see much political debate (although the two categories of labour migrants and forced migrants are either deliberately or unconsciously confused).

In chronological order, the first event since 2011 to trigger political debate about the need for Poland to admit asylum seekers was the Ukrainian crisis in late 2013, in the aftermath of which Russia invaded the territory of Ukraine in February 2014, starting the protracted war in the east of Ukraine (Donetsk and Luhansk regions). Almost immediately after the Russian aggression on Ukraine, the Polish government run by Donald Tusk (Civic Platform) started preparations for humanitarian assistance to Ukrainians by safeguarding places in accommodation centres and hospitals for potential asylum seekers. It is worth mentioning here that neither Law and Justice nor any other political party in the parliament opposed the government's stance towards Ukrainians. On the contrary, it was probably the last time when PO and PiS openly expressed an agreement on any issue. It was significant to the extent it was noticed by the Polish media ("Consent in the Sejm on Ukraine. Kaczyński applauds Tusk, Tusk – Kaczyński", TVN 2014)⁸.

The subsequent developments leading to the production of refugee discourse in Poland were more or less directly related to the "refugee crisis" of 2015. In 2015, Europe experienced an increased inflow of forced migrants coming mainly from Syria, Afghanistan, and Somalia. In the mentioned year there were 1 342 215 applications for asylum submitted in the EU and Norway and Switzerland, out of which 441 900 were submitted in Germany and 156 400 in Sweden. It needs to be highlighted that Poland did not experience an increased number of asylum seekers comparable to other EU Member States. Between 2011-2019, the highest number of applications were submitted in 2013 when 15,253 were received. In the peak years of the refugee crisis in Europe, the numbers decreased to 12,325 in 2015 and 12,319 in 2016 (Office for Foreigners 2018, 2019; Szulecka, Pachocka, Sobczak-Szelc, 2018).

The actual triggers of the fierce political and public debate on refugees in Poland were two mutually interlinked developments: the refugee relocation scheme, discussed starting in April 2015 and approved in September 2015, and the welcoming policy of the German

⁸ <https://tvn24.pl/polska/zgoda-w-sejmie-ws-ukrainy-kaczynski-bije-brawo-tuskowi-tusk-kaczynskiemu-ra399992-3350618>

Chancellor Angela Merkel, who in early 2015 started advocating for supporting asylum seekers by the EU countries and in August 2015 declared that Germany would admit all Syrian asylum seekers coming to Europe (Łotocki 2019, pp. 143-151).

In September 2015, based on a proposal of the European Commission, the Justice and Home Affairs Council (comprised of the European Union Member States' interior ministers) decided to introduce the Emergency Relocation System, a quota system for refugee relocation.⁹ It aimed at supporting the frontline states of Italy and Greece in admission of asylum seekers by relocating 160,000 refugees to other EU countries. Not without significance in the Polish context was the fact that the new system of refugee relocation was proposed by Angela Merkel.¹⁰ The Czech Republic, Hungary, Romania, and Slovakia voted against the relocation system, whereas Poland, then ruled by PM Ewa Kopacz (Civic Platform) accepted it, issuing a promise of accommodating 7200 refugees in the forthcoming years (Pędzwiatr and Legut, 2017). However, the Law and Justice party, which came to power after the October 2015 elections, disregarded Poland's commitments on this matter by first lowering the number of anticipated admissions of refugees to 400 in January 2016, and then rescinding the plans of relocation to Poland of the first 100 refugees (65 from Greece and 35 from Italy) in May 2015 (Łotocki 2019, pp. 176-177).

Another important component of the background of the migration discourse in Poland was Angela Merkel's calls for supporting and admitting asylum seekers in Europe. In August 2015 Germany decided to suspend the Dublin Procedure for Syrians, which meant that refugees from that country no longer had to be sent back to the first EU country that they entered. Later that month, Angela Merkel declared "*Wir schaffen das*" ("We can do this") with respect to admission of asylum seekers. Merkel called it a "national duty" to grant protection to hundreds of people fleeing war in Syria. On 4 September 2015, Germany and Austria opened their borders for refugees stuck in Hungary. This depiction of Germany's "Willkommenskultur," or welcome culture¹¹ was a significant factor of Poland's opposition to the implementation of the refugee relocation scheme, since from the perspective of the Law and Justice government and its foreign policy of "getting off our knees" ("Wstawanie z kolan")¹², Poland could not surrender to the dictates of Germany and Angela Merkel, responsible for inviting refugees to Europe.

The negotiations on the refugee relocation system in the EU coincided with the election campaign before the parliamentary and presidential elections in October 2015 in Poland. In consequence, the dispute on the compulsory or voluntary admission of refugees became one of the most important topics of the election campaign. Hence, probably under the pressure of opposition groups, and above all PiS, whose representatives criticized the government for an overly liberal policy towards refugees, the government of PM Kopacz was inconsistent in its policy towards immigrants, including the number that Poland agreed to admit (Stolarczyk 2017, p. 32). The media debate on this matter mirrored the political discussion. Whereas liberal *Gazeta Wyborcza* supported Ewa Kopacz's decision on admission of refugees within

⁹ COUNCIL DECISION (EU) 2015/1601 of 22 September 2015 establishing provisional measures in the area of international protection for the benefit of Italy and Greece. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32015D1601> [Accessed 3 September 2020].

¹⁰ <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/europe/germany/11561430/Angela-Merkel-calls-for-new-rules-for-distributing-asylum-seekers-in-Europe.html>

¹¹ <https://www.dw.com/en/two-years-since-germany-opened-its-borders-to-refugees-a-chronology/a-40327634>

¹² <https://www.rp.pl/Kraj/170309054-Polityka-zagraniczna-PiS-Jak-Polska-znow-wstaje-z-kolan.html>

the Emergency Relocation System, conservative newspapers and magazines strongly opposed the government's stance. The conservative magazine 'W Sieci' did not hesitate to link refugees with terrorists by presenting on its cover Ewa Kopacz wearing a burka and holding sticks of dynamite, together with the headline "Ewa Kopacz will arrange a hell for us at the behest of Berlin".¹³

The developments depicted above comprised the core of causes leading to the production of refugee and migration discourses in Poland. The subsequent terrorist attacks in Paris (13 November 2015), Brussels (22 March 2016) and Barcelona (17 August 2017) were meaningful for continuation of the discourses, since they were portrayed by the conservative and far-right newspapers as materialization of the anticipated threat, but their role should not be overestimated. Right-wing politicians and journalists inciting fear, and also the neglect of liberal groups regarding the public opinion's susceptibility to an atmosphere of danger, were far more influential in shaping the discourses.

¹³ <https://www.wirtualnemedi.pl/artykul/ewa-kopacz-pozywa-w-sieci-za-okladke-z-burka-i-dynamitem-chce-przeprosin-i-30-tys-zl-na-cel-charytatywny>

Political Speeches

Political slogans were identified to generate narrative categories reflecting diverging courses on Europeanisation in Poland in reaction to increased external migration. The slogans encompassed sayings, claims, and discourses with moral persuasion. With regard to this step of the analysis, the main research question was what do politicians demand with regard to the EU's future approach towards migration. Based on 22 speeches, the analytical grid was filled in with main themes identified through the analysis (see Appendix A).

With respect to the role of the European Union in managing the anticipated migration crisis which could have affected Poland, in 2014 all the main political parties counted on its support. Then Prime Minister Donald Tusk (Civic Platform) openly expressed his hopes for EU help in admission of asylum seekers from Ukraine if their numbers increased: *"If the influx of Ukrainians is bigger, the EU should be ready to help"* (PL3-2014-Tusk). The ruling Civic Platform saw the EU as a partner and a supporter of Poland's policy toward Eastern Europe. The migration crisis of 2015 polarised political parties' stances towards the EU's role in managing the crisis. Whereas Civic Platform highlighted that the Member States should act with solidarity towards the 'refugee crisis' and jointly share the responsibility (relocation quotas accepted), PiS raised an issue of sovereignty by stating that the EU could not limit Poland's independence in the name of the principle of solidarity by imposing refugee relocation quotas on Member States. Conservatives from PiS, but also from Civic Platform, questioned the EU's capacity to accommodate all forced migrants by arguing that the EU cannot accept everyone, and it should admit only those who are really escaping from war or conflict. Only United Left called for the need to admit asylum seekers in the spirit of European values: *"We, as Europeans, have to act with solidarity towards refugees"* (PL18-2015-Nowacka).

The indicated themes concerning Poland's (category of a Member State) desired position in dealing with the migration crisis also revealed divisions between the stances of political parties. Again, solidarity was mentioned by the Civic Platform, Modern, and the United Left, whereas sovereignty was stressed by Conservatives (PiS, Kukiz'15). Liberals raised solidarity with respect to both the solidarity principle within the EU and solidarity towards people in need (asylum seekers) related to the principle of responsibility to protect.¹⁴ Conservatives, in addition to the importance of safeguarding Poland's sovereignty, claimed that Poland is not obliged by the principle of solidarity since the country is not responsible for the reasons why refugees flee their countries. On the other hand, despite the claimed lack of responsibility for wars or conflicts in the Middle East and Africa, they also excused themselves by saying that Poland sends humanitarian aid to Syria and other countries of (refugees') origin. Another important factor for Conservatives in the debate on admission of asylum seekers was the safety of Polish citizens: *"a family and the nation (and their safety) should be put first, before others"* (PL6-2015-Kaczynski). Not surprisingly, both main parties (PO and PiS) agreed that Poland's eastern border is also the border of the European Union and the two polities have to share responsibility to protect it (see Appendix B).

The analysis of the political claims with respect to the polity category and both sub-categories the EU and the Member State revealed two characteristics pertaining to Poland.

¹⁴ Responsibility to protect is an international norm that seeks to ensure that the international community never again fails to halt the mass atrocity crimes of genocide, war crimes, ethnic cleansing and crimes against humanity. See more at: <https://www.un.org/en/genocideprevention/about-responsibility-to-protect.shtml> [Accessed 3 September 2020].

First, whereas in 2014 after the breakout of the war between Russia and Ukraine all main political parties in Poland agreed on admission of potential asylum seekers from Ukraine which was perceived as an expression of Poland's support of pro-European Ukrainian government, in 2015 stances about the need and readiness to admit asylum seekers from the Middle East started polarising. Second, since 2015 the main axis of division between political parties towards the EU has been their different understanding of the principle of solidarity¹⁵ within the EU (see Appendix B).

With regard to whom the politicians talked to (subjects) or talked about (objects), the latter approach prevailed in the analysed speeches. If politicians granted any subjectivity, it was addressed at citizens of Poland and not at migrants. Migrants (both forced and economic migrants) were treated as objects, without giving them any ability to influence their future: "refugees should not be relocated to Poland through the permanent mechanism" (PL9-2015-Gowin). Furthermore, they were often treated as a threat to the country: "there is a threat of bringing 100 thousand Muslims to Poland" (PL11-2015-Kaczynski). It also proves that political claims are an instrument of domestic politics and their role is to gain electoral support by uniting them around the classical division axis of "we versus others". This was visible in the threat arguments made by PiS: "If the influx of immigrants is not stopped, they will impose their culture and customs on us" (PL6-2015-Kaczynski) or "refugees spread dangerous diseases" (PL11-2015-Kaczynski) (see Appendix B).

With reference to the Diagnosis subcategory (Proposition), all the quoted politicians saw the seriousness of the increased forced migration to Europe, but they disagreed on the causes of the crisis. Civic Platform and Modern perceived the reason of forced migration as independent from the EU. "Syrian refugees flee from Turkey, Jordan and Lebanon due to poor conditions in camps" (PL8-2015-Schetyna) and defined a lack of coordination within the EU in the field of immigration as being the real crisis: "Actions of some countries are delayed or insufficient" (PL8-2015-Schetyna). In the opinion of Law and Justice and Kukiz'15, the EU and other Member States (in particular Germany and Angela Merkel) are equally if not more responsible for the crisis by encouraging asylum seekers to come to Europe, by not taking sufficient actions, and by not offering any efficient solution to the crisis: "It is a mistake of Merkel, and now she wants to share her mistake with other countries" (PL11-2015-Kaczynski) (see Appendix B).

The slogans related to the Prognosis subcategory (Proposition) of the analysis were the most complex and extensive in nature. Liberals (in particular United Left, and to a lesser extent Civic Platform) linked the need of admitting asylum seekers with the solidarity principle of the EU and called for acting like a responsible Member State: "We need to show that we are a mature and responsible member of the EU. Poland needs to take action in issues of refugees, asylum and migration" (PL8-2015-Schetyna). They sought a solution in a coordination and harmonisation of Member States' actions towards asylum seekers and other immigrants, simultaneously highlighting the importance of cooperation on border protection. As a long-term solution of the 'refugee crisis' they proposed peace-building in the Middle East, but without determining what actions should be included in the peace-building process. On the other hand, Law and Justice separated responsibilities of the state and the European Union. According to their claims, the competency of admission of asylum seekers should be vested

¹⁵ The principle of solidarity of the European Union is a fundamental principle based on sharing both the advantages, i.e. prosperity, and the burdens equally and justly among members.

to each Member State, and Poland, within this competency, should admit those asylum-seekers whose values and religion are close to those of Poland by saying “cultural proximity criterion when helping refugees” (PL9-2015-Gowin). Further on, if Poland admits refugees, they should be controlled by the state and eventually assimilated. To PiS, the best solution to the crisis was humanitarian and development aid sent to the countries of origin: “we want to help and we are helping, and we will develop humanitarian assistance. We carry out international projects, we engage in helping in Syria and everywhere, when people need help. But we don’t agree, Poland won’t agree on any blackmailing by the European Union” (PL20-2017-Szydło). They recognized the EU competencies in border protection and called for taking appropriate actions in this matter. Surprisingly, they agreed with Liberals with regard to the long-term solution. Here they saw the role of the EU, calling for engagement of the latter in stabilization in the Middle East and Africa (see Appendix B).

In conclusion, it needs to be reiterated that the anti-migration (or anti-refugee) narratives in Poland emerged in 2015 as a result of increased migration to the EU and the decision of relocation quotas among the Member States. As political claims analysis revealed, liberals in Poland link the obligation of admitting asylum seekers more with the solidarity principle of the EU and less with the responsibility to protect principle. They are open to admitting asylum seekers in-house, provided that they are thoroughly checked (no condition of cultural proximity).

Furthermore, conservative PiS argues that other EU countries should bear the burden of asylum seekers/refugees, claiming that Poland is not responsible for the reasons behind forced migrants fleeing their countries. According to them, the principle of solidarity cannot precede sovereignty of a Member State. They are eager to help on-site through humanitarian and development aid. Poland can admit a small number of asylum seekers, but only those of cultural (and religious) proximity.

Surprisingly, both Civic Platform and Law and Justice agree that Poland (and the EU) should better protect their borders. However, the security factor is much stronger in the latter’s claims, as they argue that Poland cannot admit asylum seekers/refugees at the expense of the security of citizens, even if threat to security is only anticipated.

Despite the different views on the EU’s role in solving the refugee crisis and recalling the arguments of conservative parties regarding the sovereignty of the nation state, no references or explicit calls for Poland’s exit from the EU were made by any of the political parties. The reason for that could be simply the voters: a positive attitude towards Poland’s EU membership has been dominant in all social-demographic groups. Even the supporters of the Law and Justice, politicians of which are known from their Euro-sceptical arguments, are generally in favour of Poland’s membership in the EU (Cichocki 2013, p. 270).

Circulation of Narratives in the Mainstream Media

This section presents the empirical findings from the second phase of the research, namely the media analysis. As such, this section analyses ideological variations in how newspapers editorialise political speeches and rhetoric, and it looks at the role of newspapers in addressing and critiquing problem-identification and claim-making about refugees, migration, and Europe. Although there is no equality between the three selected newspapers (Rzeczpospolita, Gazeta Wyborcza and Gazeta Polska Codziennie) in terms of their influence on forming the opinions of the wider public, since they differ significantly in terms of circulation, they were chosen on purpose to present different perspectives on the issues of forced migration and Europeanisation.

Similar to the political scene, in the Polish media there was no controversy on accepting potential asylum seekers from Ukraine after Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February 2014. On the contrary, all three newspapers, Rzeczpospolita, Gazeta Wyborcza and Gazeta Polska Codziennie, agreed with the need to help Ukrainians fleeing from the conflict. The minor difference was that Rzeczpospolita underlined Poland's political responsibility in both accepting Ukrainians and facilitating their migration to the EU:

The declaration to waive visas for Ukrainians should be the first flame to the fire. We need to give them the opportunity of easier travel to Union countries. Some will say that in this time of mass migration from African countries to Europe this will open up another Pandora's box, that it is unsafe for the Union's social balance. We have no doubts that this is a bogus perspective. Ukrainians were and are Europeans (RZ_03.12.13).

Gazeta Wyborcza focused on the declared aid for potential asylum seekers, and Gazeta Polska Codziennie praised the unanimity of the government and the opposition with regard to Ukraine and Ukrainians. Apparently, since admission of Ukrainians did not become an issue of political debate, neither did it attract wide attention of the media.

2015 brought an increase of media articles related to migration to the EU in general and escalation of the media debate on acceptance/non-acceptance of asylum seekers in particular. As mentioned in the Methodology section, in looking through the articles we were interested in topics of migration to Poland and to the EU with respect to forced migrants (asylum seekers and refugees). The selected articles either directly or indirectly discussed the respective discourse framings identified in the first step of the research (political claims analysis). The framings identified during the political claims analysis were grouped into three thematic blocs, according to their subject: discourses on solidarity versus sovereignty, discourses of responsibility to protect versus conservative discourses on lack of responsibility of Poland, and the discourses on the role of the European Union in solving the 'migration crisis' and the future of the European community.

Discourse framings on solidarity versus sovereignty

With respect to the first group of discourses, solidarity vs. sovereignty, the discourse analysis revealed that whereas liberal Gazeta Wyborcza praised and even called for solidarity among the EU Member States, the far-right Gazeta Polska Codziennie prioritised sovereignty,

and the centric Rzeczpospolita was inconsistent, sometimes leaning towards solidarity, and at other times towards sovereignty.

Out of the three analysed newspapers, Rzeczpospolita was the most neutral in presenting its stance or stances towards either solidarity or sovereignty in dealing with the issue of solving the migration crisis at the EU level. The newspaper often showed the situation as it was without aligning with either of the two biggest camps – PiS and PO: “Platform – by the lips of prime minister Kopacz – is proclaiming that we must maintain solidarity and share the responsibility of refugees with the other EU countries. PiS is more careful. This is not strange as everything indicates that after the fall elections, Jarosław Kaczyński’s party will have to take this problem onto their shoulders” (RZ_11.09.15). In addition, Rzeczpospolita journalists often presented contradictory opinions on the mentioned narratives. However, even supporters of acting according to solidarity among the Member States were not uncritical towards the EU decisions. Strongly criticised was the idea of imposing penalties on countries not accepting refugees through the relocation mechanism: “This idea will hurt the immigrant issue and will not give them anything because it will not be implemented (it will not gain adequate support in the European Council). It will also hurt the European Union because it provides arguments for populists and euro-sceptics. The financial penalty is part of the idea for permanent quotas of refugee distribution between EU countries, which for unknown reasons, was resurrected in Brussels” (RZ_05.05.16). Among the Rzeczpospolita journalists were also opponents of invoking the solidarity principle in regard to migration policies of particular countries: “Even if it is not so wealthy the Polish state has to spend money on newcomers from Africa, then this money will run out somewhere else. And what if the conflict in Ukraine intensifies and we face the challenge of receiving thousands of refugees not from a distant land, but from a neighboring country that is historically and culturally much closer? Where will we get the means for that? Will someone then help us in the name of solidarity?” (RZ_02.05.15). Since it was difficult to determine a cohesive stance of Rzeczpospolita in the debate between solidarity versus sovereignty, the newspaper did not offer any cohesive strategy for solving the issue.

Gazeta Wyborcza presented its stance on the debate in a more consistent way than Rzeczpospolita. The journalists expressed their support for the solidarity principle and equated politicians claims on defending sovereignty with either national egoism or nationalism. They also cared about the reputation of Poland within the European Union, and called for admitting asylum seekers at least for the sake of maintaining good relations with Brussels and other Member States: “The opposition of the Law and Justice government to the relocation of Syrians has hurt Poland greatly. We have lost the reputation of a country that can take responsibility for the community and solve European problems. By refusing solidarity from EU countries struggling with the migration crisis, our country has lost the right to demand solidarity from others” (GW_18.08.2018). In addition, the newspaper often shed a light on Law and Justice politicians’ hypocrisy in terms of acceptance solidarity from the EU if the beneficiary is Poland and rejecting it if beneficiaries are other countries: “The European politicians, especially Germans, have begun to treat Poland as a country of racists and ungrateful people. Because we eagerly take a mountain of European money and demand a tough stance against Russia for its aggression against Ukraine, and when we need help, we plea for solidarity. Warsaw was instructed that European solidarity is two-way, and that EU membership also means obligations” (GW_23.09.2015). Significantly, Wyborcza’s articles depicted sovereignty claims by the conservative right as a threat to Poland’s future in the EU: “Prime Minister Szydło’s words mean that PiS will build the ideology of a besieged fortress, sovereignty and national pride, allegedly threatened by Islam and a hostile Europe. Yet Europe, which has just

begun to rebuild around Germany and France after years of crisis, will not support a country that cares about its values. Poles has already started" (GW_18.05.2017). In the analysed articles, Wyborcza presented a rather clear solution to the issue, stating consistently that there was no alternative for Poland's integration with the EU and acting as a responsible member of the community by applying the principle of solidarity.

Conservative, far-right Gazeta Polska Codziennie mostly reproduced discourses on migration as an attack on Polish values and the relocation mechanism as an attack on Poland's sovereignty. The decisions taken by the European Council were described as coercion or a dictate (GP_10.09.2015 and GP_10.09.2015). Furthermore, journalists of GP Codziennie perceived the European Union as an external actor representing the interests of Germany and France, opposed to Poland by undermining the national interests of the latter: "the Polish government did not yield to first pressure and then blackmail from the EU and politicians from individual countries most interested in having Poland correct their mistakes. Macron or Gabriel [head of the German Ministry of Foreign Affairs], Timmermans or Avramopoulos [European Commissioner for Migration] did not intimidate the Polish authorities or society" (GP_30.09.2017). With regard to solution of the debate between solidarity and sovereignty, Gazeta Polska Codziennie consistently does not foresee a possibility to reconcile Poland's responsibilities towards these two obligations and continuously stand for defending national interests and disregarding solidarity among the members of the European Union.

Discourse framings on responsibility to protect versus lack of Poland's responsibility to admit asylum seekers

In regard to framings supporting and opposing the responsibility to protect principle, it turned out that only liberal Gazeta Wyborcza firmly reproduced the responsibility to protect discourse. Rzeczpospolita was rather reluctant to present an unambiguous stance while Gazeta Polska Codziennie reproduced discourses to support that Poland should not be held responsible to admit asylum seekers.

Starting with Gazeta Wyborcza, its journalists took the role of defenders of the responsibility to protect principle, standing in opposition to narratives circulated in the majority of the analysed politicians' speeches. They interpret the situation as the result of a conscious decision of the Polish government not to find a solution within the EU and its unwillingness to comply with the fundamental principles of the EU. They blamed Law and Justice as well as Civic Platform for replacing the humanitarian duty with a narrative of fears and threats as follows. "

No rational person is in favor of opening borders completely. Ideally, there should be no refugees, but the world is not perfect. Wars, hunger and terror are driving thousands of people out of their homes. It is a threat, but also a challenge. It forces us to answer the question of whether we want to be an open society or a closed and scared society. The Civic Platform is a better, open and European party. But the party just said that in fact, the choice between PiS and PO is just a matter of style (GW_11.05.2017).

In addition, they spared no criticism towards the European Union for not foreseeing the effects of its inaction.

What is Europe doing? She still pretends the problem isn't there. Meanwhile, in a moment, refugees will spread across the continent. We will not stop them by putting up fences on the border. People fleeing the war are so desperate that they will overcome any obstacle to find themselves in a country where they will feel safe (GW_12.08.2015).

Gazeta Wyborcza was also against differentiating asylum seekers in terms of their religion, and interpreted politicians calls for accepting only Christian asylum seekers as selfishness.

It is true that Poland is reluctant to face the challenge of solidarity towards refugees in general, and refugees from Africa and Muslims in particular. At the moment, the most popular slogan to be used by most candidates in the recent presidential election is: Let's take care of our own business! This interest is understood as so-called healthy selfishness, which has grown into a moral value" (GW_28.05.2015).

Lastly, Gazeta Wyborcza was the only newspaper out of the analysed ones to question the moral values and the system of faith behind politicians' narratives on sending humanitarian aid to Syria and other places of conflicts instead of admitting asylum seekers.

PiS politicians demonstrate their religiosity, but refuse to help those in need. They use the formula of "helping on the spot", and claim (falsely) that Poland has accepted a million refugees from Ukraine. At the same time, the PiS government is breaking international law by preventing Chechens traveling to Brest from submitting an application for asylum in Poland. The government is not reacting to the rising tide of racism, physical and verbal aggression towards refugees, immigrants, and tourists. How does this relate to Christianity?" (GW_21.08.2017).

Centrist Rzeczpospolita approached the responsibility/non-responsibility narratives more pragmatically and did not present a cohesive stance on it. Sometimes Rzeczpospolita's journalists defended limiting the number of accepted asylum seekers in order to comply with the EU solidarity principle as follows. "There is, however, another solution used by many other member states including in our region. Accepting a small group of refugees most in need. Tiny Latvia accepted a few dozen and there is probably no one left (they moved to Germany). And no one is complaining that Latvia is anti-solidarity and cruel" (RZ_27.10.16). In general, the articles did not call for not admitting asylum seekers, but were far from reproducing the responsibility to protect principle by proposing solutions which in fact undermined the principle as follows. "There is a reputational crisis from which Beata Szydło's image will need to be saved step by step. It should begin with starting humanitarian passages together with the Church. Requiring/demanding better procedures (of course automatic relocation is not an option) for accepting those most in need. Finally, accepting a group of people similar to the people of Poland who will manage well with us. And with whom we can deal with. But above all, not instilling a fear of refugees" (RZ_30.05.17). In one case they gave the subjectivity to asylum seekers themselves, when they claimed that the latter did not want to come to Poland. "Refugees did not come to and were not thrown out of Poland. They came somewhere else, but Poland will take in some of them" (RZ_13.10.15).

What was frequently reiterated in the analysed Rzeczpospolita articles were appeals to admit asylum seekers of a similar background culture to Poland's, which clearly limited the geographic area of countries of origin to Ukraine and other Eastern European countries.

The fact is that as of today we are not ready to accept a large mass of refugees from the Middle East, people who are from a different culture. We don't have any programs. The Interior Ministry says they have their own plan of action for how to organize accepting refugees. But what's next? It's unclear how the integration of newcomers in Polish society would be, for example teaching the language, educating children, etc. How long would they stay in refugee centers? What's next? Who would give them a place to live and where? No one has thought about this until now. This is probably why there is bothersome silence on this issue. (RZ_11.09.15).

With reference to a solution, Rzeczpospolita did not explicitly provide one, but the articles suggested being better prepared for the repetition of a situation with increased numbers of refugees, since future crises are more than certain:

What I am trying to bring attention to is the hard reality of global challenges that the leaders of Poland are trying to ignore. The Middle East and Africa, which is experiencing its next humanitarian crisis (but also a demographic boom), will generate more and more such problems. Regardless of whether the Polish government wants it or not, migrants will again stand at the gates of the modern world and in higher numbers than a few years ago (RZ_30.05.17).

In the articles of far-right *Gazeta Polska Codziennie* there was no trace of support for the responsibility to protect principle. On the contrary, the newspaper justified Poland's lack of responsibility for either admitting asylum seekers or complying with the solidarity principle in the EU. Journalists reproduced the arguments of Law and Justice politicians, in particular Jarosław Kaczyński, such as not being involved in colonialism or not using the migrant workforce. It read as follows "we did not exploit the countries from which refugees come today. We did not use their work, we did not invite them to Europe. We have every moral right to say, 'No!', said Kaczyński. As he emphasized, it is not only about a possible terrorist threat, but about all problems with a large number of immigrants. According to Kaczyński, there are no reasons to limit the standard of living of Poles" (GP_03.07.2017). Another practice of argumentation used by *Gazeta Polska Codziennie* was naming asylum seekers as "fake refugees" by identifying them with economic migrants as follows. "The vast majority of immigrants who press against the borders of the Schengen area, seeking social security from wealthy EU countries, do not meet the definition of a refugee defined in international law and do not come directly from the war zone. Many of them are migrants from the Balkans or the Sahel countries" (GP_25.05.2017). Last but not least, the newspaper gave priority to the security of Poland and the Polish nation and used this discourse in reacting to any terrorist attack in Europe regardless of the (non-refugee) background of the perpetrators:

What a fool (or a rascal) it takes to bring deadly terrorist threats upon your nation! This is what is happening in Western Europe. Today, France, Germany, Sweden, Belgium and Spain run the blood of innocent people through utopian dreams of multi-culti and the opening of the EU's external borders. Covering yourself with refugees is a headache. The number of real refugees fleeing war-torn Syria does not exceed 5 percent of all immigrants. And Europe cannot absorb the entire poor of Africa and Asia. Meanwhile, radical jihad is getting bolder, and Europeans are unable to withstand the growing aggression. Further bloodshed is inevitable. Summer is a period of mass

events, but it is still safe in Poland. What kind of a fool (or a rascal) must be someone who wants to change that?" (GP_19.08.2017).

Discourse framings on the role of the European Union in the migration crisis and the future of the EU

In reproducing discourses on the role of the EU in the migration crisis and the future of the European integration project, different stances among the newspapers were evident. *Gazeta Wyborcza* supported cooperation and coordination of action towards forced migration within the EU and called for maintaining the European course of Poland in order to prevent *Polexit*. *Rzeczpospolita* focused on specific areas of competencies in which the EU should be more active in responding to the increased migration and called for reform of the EU to make the organisation more efficient. *Gazeta Polska Codziennie* blamed the EU and other Member States for increased migration and all the problems stemming from it. It is not certain how the last newspaper saw the future of the European Union, because mostly it would see its dissolution or limiting it to only a free-trade area.

As the analysis confirmed, the mostly pro-European *Gazeta Wyborcza* defended the coordination role of the European crisis and called on Polish politicians to comply with the EU decision in this regard: "Europe has neither the capacity nor the moral obligation to accept everyone who wishes to live in it. However, it should involve countries that have had little burden so far to help refugees. For example, Poland, which last year granted protection to only 735 people" (GW_14.07.2014). The newspaper feared not only the prospect of Poland's exit from the EU but also about the abating rule of law in Poland. With reference to the latter, *Wyborcza* saw the EU as a guarantor of democracy in Poland from a long-term perspective, even if the European values are treated by Jarosław Kaczyński as menu in a restaurant. "Kaczyński chooses only those items that suit him, and only when he wants to. Out of the Copenhagen criteria that countries applying for admission to the EU must meet, i.e. the existence of the rule of law, institutions guaranteeing the stability of democracy, respect for human rights, and the rights of minorities, Poland under the rule of PiS does not meet virtually any" (GW_05.07.2016).

Rzeczpospolita more cautiously approached the narrative on the European Union and did not present its views rigidly, but instead suggested reconciling the interests of both actors, Poland and the EU. *Rzeczpospolita* argued that not only did Poland refrain from fulfilling its commitments with regard to the relocation mechanism, but other, much wealthier Member States did so as well as quoted below.

The quotas were voted for once in the summer of last year. To this day, no one has fulfilled them. This is hardly said – only about 1 percent of refugees that had to do with this agreement have moved. The most reluctant are the Visegrad Group and Spain, but Belgium, France and the Netherlands accepted a small number – these are wealthy countries, accustomed to immigrants and eagerly referring to "Europeanness" (RZ_05.05.16). It meant that the relocation mechanism was not a perfect solution. Therefore, the newspaper called for working out a cohesive border policy of the EU: Germany is right by requiring European solidarity on the issue of immigrants. But that solidarity should also mean the creation of a common border service, financed and maintained not only by EU border countries, but also by those that gained, thanks to the Schengen Zone, by liquidating their own border service. (RZ_18.09.15) It was apparent that *Rzeczpospolita* supported mostly the centre-right politician's slogans

about the need of better coordination mechanism within the EU: "Europe needs a common, uniform asylum policy. [...] Third, the Union should have a common refugee register and a common list of individuals suspected of terrorism (RZ_18.09.15).

Using the discussion about the failure of the coordination mechanism during the migration crisis, Rzeczpospolita called for reforms within the EU in order to achieve deeper integration.

The immigration crisis is not – contrary to Eurosceptics' opinions – proof for the idea that the European Union is being exhausted. It's exactly the opposite – it shows that Europe needs a new impulse. It needs deeper integration, not to close up in national fortresses from behind the walls of which police will shoot at storming immigrants. First, the Union needs a cohesive border policy immediately. Germany is right by requiring European solidarity in the issue of immigrants (RZ_18.09.15).

The far-right *Gazeta Polska Codziennie* proved to be the most anti-European out of the three newspapers. The articles blamed the EU, in general, and some Member States (Germany and France) in particular for the migration crisis itself. Journalists of the newspaper saw the EU as an opponent of Poland and its national interests, and accordingly all negotiations within the EU were presented as fighting between two rivals. Surprisingly, the mentioned arguments were explained as expression of a greater care of the future of Europe: "Prime Minister Morawiecki strengthened his image as an excellent head of government. More importantly, he raised a number of key issues for the future of Europe. Most of the participants in the debate, busy reading the pages of attacks on Poland, did not notice it. Meanwhile, important words were said and a politician who took Europe's problems seriously emerged" (GP_05.07.2018).

However, it is not quite sure how *Gazeta Polska Codziennie* portrayed the future of Europe, since it foresaw the collapse of the EU due to migration. This view is well described in the following poem written by a journalist from *Gazeta Polska Codziennie*:

Europe is fencing, it is fencing itself on to power,
Soon there will be no trace of Schengen.
The continent will be divided again by lines of wires and borders,
although it is known that all these treatments are for nothing.
Before the social and material incentives disappear,
until each newcomer is withdrawn.
Until the slogans as sweet as candies die
they will not roar in the seas
with all gunboat guns.
Vain summits, consultations and tons of worry.
what will debates help when there is no rescue?
You would have to order a mass for Europe, what in fear,
before Islam forbids her. (With the support of leftists) (GP_05.03.2016).

Responses of Project Stakeholders

Politicisation of migration in Poland and the issue of Europe dealing with the 'migration crisis' have had a major impact on the stakeholders involved in migration governance, in particular on social organisations politically independent of the government but financially often dependent on government funding (or EU funding, like AMIF, coordinated by government institutions). During our meso-level interviews with various stakeholders involved in multi-level migration governance our respondents from social organisations admitted that the political atmosphere and anti-migration discourse influenced their activity. On the one hand, migrant NGOs¹⁶ are busier with legal issues of their clients – migrants (including asylum seekers), while on the other hand, cuts in funding deprived them of a part of financial sources that could be used for hiring more people, such as lawyers (PLMZSO1). A practitioner from an institution directly cooperating with NGOs experienced a similar situation: "It is worse now because AMIF is on hold. Now there are more and more problems – for example, legal aid is practically non-existent. It takes a month to make an appointment at Legal Association Intervention or the Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights. But it is not related to the migration crisis" (PLMZP1). Similar to this individual, the majority of our respondents claimed that the migration crisis did not have an effect on their work, but it was the new political climate and the suspension of AMIF funding which impeded their work (PLMZSO1, PLMZSO7). Apparently, cuts in funding for NGOs affected not only social organisations but all institutions collaborating with them.

The stakeholders whom we talked to positioned themselves as either against the anti-migration discourse, or, by explaining that as public servants they could not share their private opinions on a public meeting, they responded with nothing but silence. However, there were also some attempts to defend the policy of the government: "When it comes to Poland's support for those countries that were in a serious migration crisis, Poland took part in such support missions. Dozens of people went there. Border guards were also involved in this to a much greater extent. It cannot be said that Poland did nothing at all" (MGN2R8). However, such opinions were the exception, and not common. Representatives of social organisations were much more critical towards both government policy and the political discourse on migration and refugees. One of our respondents outlined a gloomy perspective on the future of Europe, with Member States constantly contesting the EU asylum policy:

It may turn out that at some point that the European Council, looking at Hungary, Poland or the Czech Republic, will come up with the decision of deciding by qualifying majority on asylum matters, as according to the Treaty is eligible to do, so they will be binding for Poland, Hungary and the Czech Republic. This is not happening yet. But if it turns out that we finally say, okay, we will never agree on full consensus of 27 or 28 members, depending on how we count them, and just fix something by qualified majority, as the Treaty allows. The decisions against which Poland vote will be binding for Poland. It may turn out that we will stand up and say, no, we joined the Union on such principles, but we do not accept them. The question will be: How long can we stay in a situation in which we question the foundations of the functioning of the EU? (MGN2R1).

The above reflection obviously implied the question about a possible Polexit. The stakeholders seemed to agree that such a solution is not possible due to one important

¹⁶ Migrant organization in Poland is defined according to a broad sense as "a group in support of immigrants' social, cultural, or political interests". See more in: Sobczak-Szelc et al. 2020.

factor: the public opinion in Poland, meaning Poles' support for membership in the EU, even if a majority of the same Poles voted for populist or nationalist parties in the last two elections.

Another issue identified by stakeholders is undermining the rule of law by the Polish government and its impact on Poland's reputation in Europe. A practitioner from an institution of the central administration gave an example of a court ruling by the Netherlands to not send asylum seekers to Poland due to the threat to their safety. The practitioner foresaw that if other countries follow the Netherlands, Poland may be recognized as a country not safe for asylum seekers and, therefore, excluded from the Dublin regulation.

All those who pass through Poland will be able to safely travel to third countries. It will turn out that Poland, with its entire reception system, which is well evaluated by the third country courts, can turn out to be not safe for refugees from the perspective of all the things that are happening with this populist message (MGN2R11).

Last but not least, we asked the stakeholders for their opinions on the ways politicians address migrants and refugees. Our discussants agreed that due to the politicians' insisting on differentiation between economic migrants and asylum seekers, these two terms came to be associated with a negative connotation. First, economic migrants have been treated as bad because they lie about their situation and want to benefit from social assistance by pretending to be asylum seekers. Second, asylum seekers became equated with Muslims, who play the role of the classic 'other' in Polish culture and are associated with all negative features, including terrorism, religious fundamentalism, and disrespectful behaviour towards women. The same identifications are reproduced by Polish media: "The image of a refugee in the Polish press or in the Polish media it is actually an image of a Muslim, not a refugee" (MGN2R11). Although the media are not innocent of such a negative depiction of refugees, the ones who should be blamed first are the politicians who incite religious hatred. The stakeholders expressed indignation at politicians' ignorance and their lack of responsibility for the hate speech they produce (MGN2R6).

Interestingly, among our stakeholders were also representatives of the Catholic Church, who openly stood out against the anti-migration discourse and criticized the government policy and inaction towards asylum seekers: "the category of a refugee does not have an adjective. It does not have a faith or nationality. If we are talking about the Gospel, clearly there are 'visitors', without specifying any adjective. It is also important. I have been in a situation where I heard, this help will be directed to Christians. Distribution of this aid was ceded to one of the Catholic bishops there. Fortunately, he turned out to be much wiser and gave this help to both, and asked me for absolution and a blessing that he acted in a Christian way" (MGN2R5).

The above quotation is particularly important in terms of identification of the ruling Law and Justice party members with the Catholic faith and values. The representatives of the Catholic Church whom we talked to assured they tried to reach the government in order to change its approach to asylum seekers, but did not see a willingness among politicians to listen to them.

Instead of concluding this part with a summary, another quotation will be presented, a voice from academia this time. It is important, since it sheds more light on the real picture of

the division of Poland between Liberalism and Conservatism with regard to migration and Europeanisation issues:

Of course, the issue of securitization, and the issue of migration in Poland in general, are very strongly related to the politicization of one particular group of migrants, people who fled from war or different crises. These issues have many dimensions. There are tons of tropes used in the media and rightly here are some of them and they are common. One of the things I have a problem with is that it is such an unambiguous definition of the camps, because I have the impression that it is extremely intertwined. In the conservative camp I know many actors who have a very liberal approach to the issue of refugees and asylum seekers. On the other hand, in the liberal camp too you can find many people who insult Muslims and contribute significantly to Islamophobia as a form of racism. That is why for me it would be very important to precisely define what exactly is behind the Liberals and reveal the chiaroscuro, because for me it is too much of a black and white image (MGN2R17).

Conclusion

The RESPOND research on narratives on (forced) migration and Europeanisation in Poland revealed that these two issues are closely related to each other in both discourses: the one produced by politicians and the one reproduced by media. Even more interestingly, it revealed the difficulty in aligning a particular political party with one ideology and name their leaders as unequivocally Liberal or Conservative, since the slogans produced by one political party, or even by one politician (e.g. former Prime Minister Ewa Kopacz) can sometimes recall European values and sometimes nationalism veiled under cover of national security. Out of the two biggest political parties, the currently ruling Law and Justice and the opposition Civic Platform, the latter is definitely more pro-European than the first one with respect to openness on migration and even readiness to comply with the solidarity principle among the Member States regarding asylum policy. However, both PiS and PO appeared to be rather conservative than liberal. Even if PiS much more often raised the issue of sovereignty in justifying not implementing the EU decision on refugee relocation, PO referred to national security and reproduced the discourse about refugees posing a threat to security. Finally, it appeared that the political party system in Poland and lack of an influential left or social democratic party strong enough to be among the dominant forces in the parliament impacted the traditional division of Liberal and Conservative parties and led to conservative dominance of the political discourse.

The media analysis revealed that the selected newspapers present a much wider picture of the issue of forced migration issue, and they give arguments not raised by the politicians. *Gazeta Wyborcza* could be named a Liberal Europeaniser by first calling for admission of refugees due to obligations stemming from both morality and international law, and second by defending the solidarity principle within the European Union and warning politicians and readers about the consequences of breaching the commitments made before joining the community. *Rzeczpospolita* could be named as Conservative, as being critical of the unreflective decision on the refugee relocation mechanism and leaning towards narratives on admission asylum seekers of cultural proximity. On the other hand, *Rzeczpospolita* should still be recognized as pro-European, since it calls for the enhanced coordination mechanism within the EU towards migration and raises a need to reform the EU in order to make the organisation more effective in facing the future crises. Out of the analysed newspapers it was *Gazeta Polska Codziennie* which most often reproduced the anti-migration discourses produced by the Law and Justice politicians. While the slogans against admission of refugees due to the threat to security or due to lack of responsibility for crises which made them flee their countries could be termed populist with respect to politicians, in *Gazeta Polska Codziennie* they had clear far-right undertones.

Stakeholders understood the reproduction of anti-migration and anti-EU discourses in a broader socio-political context, including the prospect for the future of Poland's membership in the EU and the future of the European community itself. Stakeholders agreed that there is no alternative to integration with the EU, but were worried about a diminishing role of Poland within the community caused by the Polish government's approach to the fundamental principles of the EU (the solidarity principle, but also rule of law, human rights with reference to LGBTQ minority rights, and others). The existing anti-migration discourses as a factor interrelated with PiS government policy impacted the daily work of the Stakeholders to a various extent. The most affected were the NGOs which lost financial sources due to

suspension of AMIF funding in 2016. It has to be added that the situation was also not easy for public institutions which either work with asylum seekers as part of the reception system (Office for Foreigners) or deal with defending the rights of various vulnerable groups, including asylum seekers (Ombudsman). To conclude, the situation of diverging from the pro-European path by the Polish government has been perceived as difficult for all stakeholders.

Appendices

Appendix A. Political speeches selected to the analysis

No	Type of speech act	Date	Politician	Function	Political party	Code
1	Parliamentary speech (expose)	20.03.2013	Radosław Sikorski	Foreign Affairs Minister	Civic Platform (Platforma Obywatelska)	PL1-2013-Sikorski
2	Parliamentary speech	10.10.2013	Robert Biedroń	Member of Parliament	Civic Platform (Platforma Obywatelska)	PL2-2013-Biedroń
3	Parliamentary speech	19.02.2014	Donald Tusk	Prime Minister	Civic Platform (Platforma Obywatelska)	PL3-2014-Tusk
4	Speech at the celebration of the 10th anniversary of Poland joining the EU	01.05.2014	Bronisław Komorowski	President	Civic Platform (Platforma Obywatelska)	PL4-2014-Komorowski
5	Speech at the celebration of the 10th anniversary of Poland joining the EU	01.05.2014	Donald Tusk	Prime Minister	Civic Platform (Platforma Obywatelska)	PL5-2014-Tusk
6	Parliamentary speech	16.09.2015	Jarosław Kaczyński	Leader of the opposition party	Law and Justice (Prawo i Sprawiedliwość)	PL6-2015-Kaczyński
7	Parliamentary speech	16.09.2015	Ewa Kopacz	Prime Minister	Civic Platform (Platforma Obywatelska)	PL7-2015-Kopacz
8	Parliamentary speech	16.09.2015	Grzegorz Schetyna	Foreign Affairs Minister	Civic Platform (Platforma Obywatelska)	PL8-2015-Schetyna
9	Parliamentary speech	16.09.2015	Jarosław Gowin	Member of Parliament	Polska Razem (Poland Together, an opposition party)	PL9-2015-Gowin
10	Parliamentary speech	16.09.2015	Rafał Trzaskowski	Vice Minister of Foreign Affairs	Civic Platform (Platforma Obywatelska)	PL10-2015-Trzaskowski
11	Election campaign speech (before parliamentary elections)	15.10.2015	Jarosław Kaczyński	Leader of the opposition party	Law and Justice (Prawo i Sprawiedliwość)	PL11-2015-Kaczyński

12	Political party leaders debate before the parliamentary elections	21.10.2015	Ewa Kopacz	Prime Minister, Party leader	Civic Platform (Platforma Obywatelska)	PL12-2015-Kopacz
13	Political party leaders debate before the parliamentary elections	21.10.2015	Beata Szydło	Candidate for Prime Minister from PiS	Law and Justice (Prawo i Sprawiedliwość)	PL13-2015-Szydło
14	Political party leaders debate before the parliamentary elections	21.10.2015	Paweł Kukiz	Party leader	Kukiz'15	PL14-2015-Kukiz
15	Political party leaders debate before the parliamentary elections	21.10.2015	Adrian Zandberg	Party leader	Together (now Left Together)	PL15-2015-Zandberg
16	Political party leaders debate before the parliamentary elections	21.10.2015	Janusz Piechociński	Party leader	Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe (Polish People's Party)	PL16-2015-Piechociński
17	Political party leaders debate before the parliamentary elections	21.10.2015	Janusz Korwin-Mikke	Party leader	KORWIN - Koalicja Odnowy Rzeczypospolitej Wolność i Nadzieja (KORWIN - Coalition for the Renewal of the Republic – Liberty and Hope)	PL17-2015-Korwin-Mikke
18	Political party leaders debate before the parliamentary elections	21.10.2015	Barbara Nowacka	Leader of United Left (Zjednoczona Lewica)	United Left (Zjednoczona Lewica)	PL18-2015-Nowacka
19	Political party leaders debate before the parliamentary elections	21.10.2015	Ryszard Petru	Party leader	Modern (Nowoczesna)	PL19-2015-Petru
20	Parliamentary speech	24.05.2017	Beata Szydło	Prime Minister	Law and Justice (Prawo i Sprawiedliwość)	PL20-2017-Szydło
21	Party convention speech	01.07.2017	Jarosław Kaczyński	Party leader	Law and Justice Party (PiS)	PL21-2017-Kaczyński

22	Speech in the European Parliament	04.07.2018	Mateusz Morawiecki	Prime Minister	Law and Justice Party (Prawo i Sprawiedliwość)	PL22-2018-Morawiecki
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Appendix B. Analysis of politicians' speeches - Poland

Categories of Analysis	Sub-Categories	Themes
Polity (on behalf of what is he/she speaking)	EU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All Europe should be engaged in Ukraine's future (PL3-2014-Tusk) If the influx of Ukrainians is bigger, the EU should be ready to help (PL3-2014-Tusk) EU should back Poland's foreign policy towards Eastern Europe (PL3-2014-Tusk) Poland and the UE should show solidarity towards Ukrainian conflict (PL3-2014-Tusk) The whole of Europe is threatened by Muslim immigrants (PL6-2015-Kaczyński, see priceless quotation 1) The responsibility for refugee protection should be divided according to GDP share in the EU (PL6-2015-Kaczynski) Europe is a safe place, where people can find refuge (PL7-2015-Kopacz) The EU cannot afford to help all and admit everyone (PL10-2015-Trzaskowski) We will keep solidarity with the EU and with refugees (PL12-2015-Kopacz) We, as Europeans, have to act with solidarity towards refugees (PL18-2015-Nowacka)
	Member State	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Poland is ready to accept potential Ukrainian refugees without any special procedures (PL3-2014-Tusk) Poland offers medical treatment to injured Ukrainians and Ukrainian refugees (PL3-2014-Tusk) The family and the nation should be put first, before others (PL6-2015-Kaczynski) Poland is not guilty of the situation in the Middle East (PL6-2015-Kaczynski) Right to defend our sovereignty in the EU (PL6-2015-Kaczynski) The Polish border is not protected at all against potential transport of weapons (PL6-2015-Kaczynski) Being a member of the EU raises the duty of solidarity (PL7-2015-Kopacz) We need to pay back solidarity which was showed to us by the EU (PL7-2015-Kopacz) We should show solidarity towards those who die in the Mediterranean Sea (PL7-2015-Kopacz) The government needs to guarantee security to its citizens (PL7-2015-Kopacz) Poland is a model example of safeguarding the external border of the EU (PL8-2015-Schetyna) We want to show solidarity towards refugees, but we need to take complex and responsible actions (PL8-2015-Schetyna) We cannot wait, be silent or find a simple, golden solution (PL8-2015-Schetyna) No country can escape from solidarity (PL8-2015-Schetyna) Due to location of Frontex, we have a special responsibility (PL8-2015-Schetyna) We need immigrants in Poland due to the large demographic gap (PL9-2015-Gowin) We don't have a holistic migration policy (PL9-2015-Gowin) The core of the immigration policy should be a repatriation policy (PL9-2015-Gowin) We cannot turn our back on the EU during the refugee crisis (PL10-2015-Trzaskowski) We should show solidarity with other UE member states (PL10-2015-Trzaskowski) We can admit refugees only in a safe way (PL19-2015-Petru) We don't share a utopia of open borders (PL20-2017-Szydło) We offer humanitarian help to Syria and other countries (PL20-2017-Szydło, see priceless quotation 6)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Poland is being blackmailed by the EU (PL20-2017-Szydlo, see priceless quotation 6) We protect external borders of the EU (PL20-2017-Szydlo, see priceless quotation 7) We won't agree on political correctness (PL20-2017-Szydlo, see priceless quotation 9) We won't agree on social disaster only because we take money from the EU (PL21-2017-Kaczynski) We have a moral right to say "no" (PL21-2017-Kaczynski) <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> We appreciate the EU money, but we can have different opinions (PL21-2017-Kaczynski) Poland hosts 1.5 million Ukrainians, who could be refugees but are not registered as such (PL22-2018-Morawiecki, see priceless quotation 10)
	Neighbouring state	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Visas with Georgia, Ukraine, Moldavia and Russia should be abolished (PL1-2013-Sikorski) Small border traffic is beneficial to Poland and Russia (PL1-2013-Sikorski) Greater openness of the borders is beneficial to the Polish economy (PL1-2013-Sikorski) Poland's policy toward Ukraine should be Europeanised (PL3-2014-Tusk) Polish cities cooperate with Russia owing to small border traffic (PL5-2014-Tusk) Our eastern neighbours are jealous of the Polish success of being a member of the EU for 10 years (PL5-Tusk-2014)
Actors (TCNs/citizens)	Object (talked about)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need to differentiate between refugees escaping from war and economic migrants (PL6-2015-Kaczynski) Economic migrants are a problem of Germany, since Germany attracted them (PL6-2015-Kaczynski) Admitting refugees from Chechnya did not increase the threat of terrorism (PL7-2015-Kopacz) A need to differentiate between refugees and economic migrants (PL7-2015-Kopacz) There is no influx of immigrants into Poland (PL7-2015-Kopacz) We need to verify the identity of immigrants (PL7-2015-Kopacz) Illegal migration (PL8-Schetyna-2015) We should differentiate economic migrants from refugees (PL9-2015-Gowin) Refugees should not be relocated to Poland through the permanent mechanism (PL9-2015-Gowin) There is a threat of bringing 100 thousand Muslims to Poland (PL11-2015-Kaczynski) Refugees spread dangerous diseases (PL11-2015-Kaczynski) They are not refugees, but economic immigrants (PL14-2015-Kukiz) Accepting refugees means accepting terrorism (PL20-2017-Szydlo) We didn't call immigrants (PL21-2017-Kaczynski) There is no reason to decrease the standard of living in Poland due to immigration (PL21-2017-Kaczynski)
	Subject (talked to)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Poland should not differentiate between Christian and non-Christian refugees from Syria (PL2-2013-Biedron) If the influx of immigrants is not stopped, they will impose their culture and customs on us (PL6-2015-Kaczynski) Help only if it is safe for the Poles (PL6-2015-Kaczynski) We cannot build a wall and say we are self-sufficient in the eyes of Europe (PL7-2015-Kopacz) The most important is security of the country and the citizens (PL20-2017-Szydlo)
	Diagnosis	Member State:

<p>Propositions (migration related)</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the government wants to admit immigrants, it means it is carrying out a German agenda (PL14-2015-Kukiz) • Refugees escape from Poland to Germany due to higher social benefits (PL17-2015-Korwin-Mikke) • We didn't colonize countries sending refugees (PL21-2017-Kaczynski) <hr/> <p>EU:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The biggest humanitarian crisis in Europe (PL7-2015-Kopacz) • Syrian refugees flee from Turkey, Jordan and Lebanon due to poor conditions in camps (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • Smuggling refugees to Europe has become a highly profitable business (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • Dublin regulation is breached (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • Refugees coming to Greece, Macedonia, Serbia, Hungary, and Austria are not registered (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • Actions of some countries are delayed or insufficient (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • There are too many declarations, promises and emotions in the EU (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • Relocation of refugees who fled to Europe is not sufficient action (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • Terrorism threat increases due to immigrants from Muslim countries (PL9-2015-Gowin) • It is a mistake of Merkel, and now she wants to share her mistake with other countries (PL11-2015-Kaczynski) • The solution proposed by the EU is bad (PL13-2015-Szydlo) • Refugee crisis is an effect of lack of coordination in the EU (PL19-2015-Petru) • Madness of the Brussel elites (PL20-2017-Szydlo, see priceless quotation 7) • It is an attack on Europe, on our culture, on our tradition (PL20-2017-Szydlo, see priceless quotation 8) • Refugees admission weakens countries in Africa and the Middle East (PL22-2018-Morawiecki)
	<p>Prognosis</p>	<p>EU:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peace in Syria should be discussed in the United Nations – discussion in the EU is not enough (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • Promise only what you can deliver (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • The external borders of the EU must be guarded better (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • Bringing back stability in the regions where refugees flee from (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • Agreeing on a list of safe countries for refugees (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • We need to strengthen joint actions on external borders of the EU (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • Need of a holistic approach: safeguarding the borders, differentiation between economic migrants and refugees, identity check and verification (PL10-2015-Trzaskowski) • There is no threat of uncontrolled influx of immigrants (PL10-2015-Trzaskowski) • Building peace in the Middle East as a solution (PL18-2015-Nowacka) • The EU must better protect the borders (PL19-2015-Petru) • Financial help to Turkey and Serbia for keeping the refugees (PL19-2015-Petru) • Europe should wake up or it will mourn her children (PL20-2017-Szydlo, see priceless quotation 8) • The EU's approach to migration should be intelligent and flexible (PL22-2018-Morawiecki) • The EU should engage in stabilization of the Middle East and Africa (PL22-2017-Morawiecki, see priceless quotation 11)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European fund of development for Africa (PL22-2018-Morawiecki, see priceless quotation 11) • The idea of external hotspots for refugees (PL22-2018-Morawiecki) <p>Member State:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We want to admit only those who really need help (PL7-2015-Kopacz) • We need to show that we are a mature and responsible member of the EU (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • Poland needs to take action in issues of refugees, asylum, and migration (PL8-2015-Schetyna) • Poland should demand the EU stop the influx of refugees (PL9-2015-Gowin) • The cultural proximity criterion when helping refugees (PL9-2015-Gowin) • Expectation of assimilation policy towards refugees in Poland (PL9-2015-Gowin) • The Border Guard should control centres for refugees (PL9-2015-Gowin) • Hot spots in order to select refugees from economic immigrants (PL12-2015-Kopacz) • Humanitarian help in order to help people to stay in their countries (PL13-2015-Szydło) • It is our moral duty to admit refugees (PL15-2015-Zandberg) • Humanitarian help as a solution (PL16-2015-Piechocinski) • The most effective help is help for the sending countries (PL20-2017-Szydlo, see priceless quotation 5) • We are ready to double our help for other countries (PL22-2018-Morawiecki)
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Priceless Quotations

1. *I would like to say, that the thing is not to accept the specific number of foreigners, regardless of who they are. The thing is, that there is a serious danger, that the following process would be triggered: at first, a number of foreigners grows dynamically, then they do not or do not want to observe our law, our customs. And then, or simultaneously, they impose their sensibility and their stipulations in the public space, in different spheres of life, in a very aggressive and impetuous way. If somebody says that this is not true, he/she should look around Europe, look at least at Sweden. There are 54 zones where sharia law is binding, and there is no state control. (PL6-2015-Kaczynski)*
2. *People fear to hang the Swedish flag in schools, this is a custom there, because there is a cross on the flag. It turns out that Swedish girls, pupils, cannot wear short clothes, because it is something not perceived well. What is going on in Italy? Occupied churches, sometimes treated as toilets even. What is going on in France? A never-ending fight, introduced sharia law, patrols who watch observing the sharia law. The same in London, and in the strongest, the hardest regarding this issue, Germany – such phenomena also take place. Do you want this in Poland? That we are no longer hosts in our country? Do you want this? (PL6-2015-Kaczynski)*
3. *Today we are aware that we are in the European Union, that we are in this great European Community, but being part of this community carries obligations. Today, turning our back on the people who need help of this great European family has resulted that we, morally and mentally, are withdrawing from this community. Today we are not in Germany, where there are 800 thousand refugees, we are not in Italy, not in Greece, not in Hungary, where there are thousands of emigrants. Today we are in Poland, where not too long ago we decided, that we would accept 200 Syrians, Christians. Now there are only 120 of them, because 80 already left. And let's remember the 1990's, when Poland was a much poorer country than now, and we accepted 86 thousand Chechens. Did you observe terrorists on every street corner? Did you witness a drop in employment? Did you notice any situations which would threaten security of Poles? (PL7-2015-Kopacz)*
4. *You have to remember that the problem of refugees will not end on 25 of October [the date of the parliamentary elections in Poland – JS]. It will last for years. We, the Poles, at any moment can be in a hard position due to the dynamic situation in the east of Europe and the east of Ukraine. We expect help and solidarity with Poland when we need it. I want to assure you that, the same as in life, in politics solidarity should work both ways. Today it is Europe and our partners in Europe who expect solidarity from us. (PL7-2015-Kopacz)*
5. *The diametrical difference between us and the opposition is the following: the government absolutely does not agree with utopia of uncontrolled opening of the borders. We are able to see threats stemming from it. We believe that the most efficient help is where the problem starts. I don't know what the opposition can offer in this matter – you changed your mind so many times that it is difficult to distinguish the truth from the manipulation – but it is worth remembering that decisions of the government of the Civic Platform and Ewa Kopacz would force us to accept a significant number of immigrants... (PL20-2017-Szydło)*
6. *All the more we want to help and we are helping, and we will develop humanitarian assistance. We carry out international projects, we engage in helping in Syria and*

everywhere, when people need help. But we don't agree, Poland won't not agree to any blackmail by the European Union. (PL20-2017-Szydło)

- 7. We won't participate in the madness of the Brussels elites. We want to help people, but not the political elites. And as I reiterate, we are helping and we will be helping – but those, who need help and wait there, in place. The Polish Border Guard engages in protecting the external borders of the European Union. (PL20-2017-Szydło)*
- 8. I am brave to say, I am brave to raise a question to the political elites in Europe – Where are you heading? Where are you heading, Europe? Get up from your knees and wake up from the lethargy, because otherwise every day you will mourn your children. If you don't see that today the terrorist threat is a fact which can take place in every country in Europe. And if you think that Poland should not defend herself, you align with those who take up weapons against Europe, against all of us. It needs to be said clearly and loudly: it is an attack on Europe, on our culture and our tradition. (PL20-2017-Szydło)*
- 9. Because being in the European Union doesn't mean agreeing on political correctness, but this is also taking responsibility when political elites in Brussels cannot take this responsibility, blinded by the political correctness and fearful, and allow taking away their guns. (PL20-2017-Szydło)*
- 10. Last week's summit of the European Council showed that the UE is capable of realism and rebuilding trust in her citizens, who wants to have safe and protected borders and a right to have influence on decisions on migration policy. The EU is struggling with influx of immigrants and refugees from different places and only a smart and flexible attitude towards the migration challenge can rebuild a sense of security of European citizens. Poland is a new home for over 1.5 million citizens of Ukraine, and many of those fled from their homes due to the Russian invasion. They are not registered as refugees in Poland only because our procedures allow them to obtain a work permit in a easier way and to build prosperity for them and for their families, owing to which they support our economy and the economy of the European Union. (PL22-2018-Morawiecki)*
- 11. The demographic pressure from the outside, especially from Africa and the Middle East will only increase. Therefore the European Union has to engage in stabilization and development of these regions. Today, a new Marshall Plan for Africa is a necessity, as is the necessity to fight against illegal smuggling of people to Europe. We support creating new funds for Africa, like the European EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa, but we propose even more. We propose creating a European fund for development of Africa and I declare that Poland wants to participate in such help – in giving a rod instead of a fish – in a greater extent than it stems from our GDP. And this is not only a declaration. We did so regarding our participation in the European Resilience Initiative built by the European Investment Bank. (PL22-2018-Morawiecki)*

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